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Ion Exchange Behaviour of Some Lanthanides and Actinides on the Derivatives of Polyvalent Metal Salt : Titanium Arsenomolybdate

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LITERATURE reveals that these days the characteristics of inorganic ion exchange materials are being credited towards achieving separations of lanthanides, actinides, heavy metals and of radiochemical interest. It has been also found that the derivatives of polyvalent metal salts are superior to their simple salts. Titanium phosphosilicate (TPS)¹, zirconium titaniumphosphate (ZTP)^{2,3} and zirconium phosphosilicate (ZPS)⁴ have been employed for the separations of some rare earths and fission products from mineral acids.

In continuation of earlier studies⁵⁻¹² on ion exchange materials of polyvalent metals, this is a part of extended approach towards their derivatives. The present report deals with the synthesis, characterisation and ion exchange behaviour of titanium arsenomolybdate. Its analytical potentiality has been explored with the quantitative separations of lanthanides from heavy metals.

Experimental

Titanium tetrachloride (B. D. H., England), arsenic acid (B. D. H.), ammonium molybdate (E. Merck) and other reagents were used of analytical grade.

The following instruments were used; Spekol u.v., Philips pH meter, Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer, muffle furnace and electric shaker.

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Synthesis of titanium arsenomolybdate (TAM) :

TAM was prepared by adding 0.15 M TiCl₄ solution to a mixture of 0.2 M arsenic acid and ammonium molybdate containing a few ml sulphuric acid in different volume ratios as indicated in Table 1. pH of the mixture was adjusted by the addition of ammonia. The remaining part of the synthesis was similar to that for other ion exchange materials.

Chemical composition :

200 mg of TAM (S₄) was dissolved in conc. H₂SO₄ and HCl. Titanium¹³ with 4-hydroxy phenyl arsenic acid and molybdenum as molybdenum¹⁰ sulphide were determined gravimetrically while arsenic¹⁴ was determined titrimetrically. The mole ratio in the sample was found as Ti : As : Mo :: 2.2 : 1 : 1.6.

Dissolution of TAM (S₄) :

100 mg of the exchanger was taken in 50 ml of the solution concerned. After shaking for 6 hr the undissolved part of the exchanger was removed by filtration. Titanium¹⁵, arsenic¹⁶ and molybdenum¹⁷ were determined spectrophotometrically.

Distribution studies :

The distribution coefficients K_d on TAM (S₄) phase were determined in DMW and 0.1 M HNO₃ solution as usual. The loading for cations was less than 3% of the ion exchange capacity. Uranium was determined spectrophotometrically while the other cations were titrated with 2 mM EDTA solution.

pH titration :

pH titrations were performed by Topper and Peppor method¹⁹. The material exhibited monofunctional behaviour.

Heat treatment :

Sample S₄ was treated at different temperatures in muffle furnace for 1 hr and ion exchange capacities (i. e. c.) were found to be 1.48 meq/g at 40° and 0.22 meq/g at 600°. IR spectra of the samples heated at different temperatures were taken by KBr disc method.

Column operation :

For separation studies 30 × 0.3 cm bore glass column was used and 1.00 g TAM (S₄) was kept in column with glass wool support. The rate of flow was 9 to 10 drops per min.

Results and Discussion

Various samples of TAM have been prepared at different pH and in different mixing ratios. Table 1 shows that the material attains high i.e.c. at higher pH. I.E.C. decreases on refluxing in arsenic acid and this might be due to the formation of new phases of TAM. On refluxing, the material turns towards powdery form while the unrefluxed material

TABLE 1—CONDITIONS OF PREPARATIONS AND I.E.C. OF TITANIUM ARSENO MOLYBDATE

Sample No.	Reagents			Mixing ratios Ti : As : Mo	pH of mixture	I.E.C. for Na ⁺ (meq/g)		Remarks
	TiCl ₄	Arsenic acid	Ammonium molybdate			UR	R	
S ₁	0.15 M	0.20 M	0.20 M	2 : 1 : 1	0	0.30	0.20	—
S ₂	0.15 M	0.20 M	0.20 M	1 : 1 : 1	1	0.65	0.40	—
S ₃	0.15 M	0.20 M	0.20 M	1 : 1 : 1	2	1.20	1.00	Stable
S ₄	0.15 M	0.20 M	0.20 M	3 : 1 : 2	2	1.46	0.94	Stable

UR=unrefluxed material ; R=refluxed material

possesses good physical appearance, mechanical strength and well suited qualities for column operation. On the basis of these, sample S₄ was chosen for detailed study.

TAM (S₄) shows better chemical stability than Sn-Mo-As¹⁸ in mineral acid solutions while both exhibit poor stability in alkaline medium.

The ion exchange capacity decreases on heating at higher temperatures which is mainly due to the condensation of hydroxyl groups and the conversion of acidic parts into their corresponding oxides.

The ir spectra of heated phases of TAM (S₄) show the absence of the bands at 3360, 2980, 2800 and 1580 cm⁻¹ while these were observed in the spectrum of the sample dried at 40°. The disappearance of these bands also supports the contention regarding the condensation of hydroxyl groups (heat sensitive groups) at higher temperatures.

A study for K_d values of some metal ions on TAM (S₄) in DMW and 0.1 M HNO₃ solutions presents the following preferential sequence :

TABLE 2—SEPARATION FACTORS (Q) FOR SOME GROUPS OF CATIONS

Sl. No.	Separation factors	DMW	0.1 M HNO ₃
1.	Q _{Hg} ^{La}	137.7	30.07
2.	Q _{Hg} ^{Ce}	182.5	32.25
3.	Q _{Hg} Th	8.07	4.62
4.	Q _{Hg} ^U	7.36	2.88
5.	Q _{Pb} ^{La}	111.45	19.09
6.	Q _{Pb} ^{Ce}	147.64	20.47
7.	Q _{Pb} Th	6.53	2.91
8.	Q _{Pb} ^U	5.98	1.83
9.	Q _{Th} ^{La}	17.07	6.55
10.	Q _{Th} ^{Ce}	22.61	7.03
11.	Q _U ^{La}	18.64	10.46
12.	Q _U ^{Ce}	24.69	11.22

To elaborate the possibilities of separations, the separation factors (Q_M^N) have been calculated and are listed in Table 2. A glance at these Q_M^N values reflects the possibility for a number of separations. Out of these the separations of Pb(II) and Hg(II) from La(III) and Ce(III) have been achieved quantitatively within the experimental elution error range.

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